

zenodo

“A Study To Assess Effectiveness Of Structured Teaching Programme On Knowledge Regarding Awareness About Sexual Abuse Among Adolescent Girls At Selected High Schools In Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh”

Priya Mishra¹, Nazia Zaidi², Gulfshan³

¹MSc Nursing Final Year, ²Assistant Professor, ³Nursing Tutor

Hind College of Nursing

U.P, India

*Corresponding Author Email: naziazaidi07@gmail.com

Date of Publication: 20/05/2026

Abstract: The present study entitled “A study to assess the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding awareness about sexual abuse among adolescent girls at selected High Schools in Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh”. Sexual abuse among adolescents is a major public health concern with lasting physical and psychological effects. Many adolescents lack adequate knowledge to protect themselves, emphasizing the need for preventive education. This study is a preliminary investigation of the extent of knowledge regarding sexual abuse and sexual abuse level in a high school where sampled were 60 (class ninth & tenth students).

Objective and Methods: The study was conducted with the objective to---1.To assess the pre-test and post-test level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls. 2.To evaluate the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls.3.To find out the association between pre-test level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls with their selected socio-demographic variables. The researcher used pre- experimental research design. The research approach was quantitative approach. The study was conducted in Pioneer Montessori High School, Barabanki. 60 samples were selected by using random sampling technique. The tool used were socio demographic profile, and structured knowledge questionnaire.

Result: The study finding revealed that majority of adolescent girls 31 had average knowledge regarding sexual abuse, 27 adolescent girls had good knowledge regarding sexual abuse, and 2 adolescent girls were having poor knowledge regarding sexual abuse. Overall mean score on knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls was 20.13 shows average knowledge. There was significant association found between standard of studying ($\chi^2=8.92>P=5.99$) and source of information ($\chi^2=18.94>P=12.48$) at 0.05 level of significance.

Interpretation and Conclusion: The overall findings of the study clearly showed that majority of adolescent girls had average knowledge regarding sexual abuse.

Keywords: Sexual abuse, knowledge, adolescent.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Adolescence word comes from the Latin word adolescence meaning “to grow up” is a transitional stage of physical and mental human development generally occurring between puberty and legal adulthood (age of majority). According to Erik Erikson's stages of human development, adolescent is a person between the ages of 13-19 year.^[1] It is often stated that girls are the world's most valuable resources and assets, but their rights throughout the world are largely ignored often resulting into tragic outcomes. This is because of the vulnerability of girls. From infancy to adolescence, girls are dependent on parents for safety and ongoing nurturing and this puts them at risk of maltreatment in many forms.^[2]

Adolescence age is a critical time to inspire and empower girls in the pivotal years. But when conflicts or crises displace adolescent girls from their homes, families and schools, they face heightened risks of exploitation, sexual and gender-based violence and early pregnancy. Their education is often disrupted, and many are forced into early marriage. Yet with the right skills and resources, adolescent girls can transform themselves, their families, their communities and their societies.^[3]

Sexual abuse also referred to as molestation, is the forcing of undesired sexual behavior by one person upon another. When that force is immediate, of short duration, or infrequent, it is called sexual assault.

zenodo

www.scientificjournal.in

YEAR: 2026

VOLUME: 4

ISSUE: 1

ISSN: 3107-4162

The offender is referred to as sexual abuser or molester. When the victim is younger than the age of consent, it is referred to as child sexual abuse.^[4]

The global prevalence of sexual abuse has been estimated at 19.7% for females and 7.9% for males, according to a 2009 study published in Clinical Psychology Review that examined 65 studies from 22 countries. Using the available data, the highest prevalence rate of sexual abuse geographically was found in Africa (34.4%), primarily because of high rates in South Africa; Europe showed the lowest prevalence rate (9.2%); America and Asia had prevalence rates between 10.1% and 23.9% respectively. Most sexual abuse offenders are known their victims; approximately 30% are relatives of the girl, most often brothers, fathers, uncles or cousins; around 60% are other acquaintances such as 'friends' of the family, babysitters, or neighbors; strangers are the offenders in approximately 10% of sexual abuse cases.^[5]

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding awareness about sexual abuse among adolescent girls at selected high school in Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh.”

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1.To assess the pre-test and post-test level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls.
- 2.To evaluate the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls.
- 3.To find out the association between pre-test level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls with their selected socio-demographic variables

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

H1:- There will be significant difference between the pre-test and post-test level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls

H2:-There will be a significant association between the pre-test level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls with their selected socio demographic variables.

H0- There will be no significant difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge of adolescent girls regarding awareness of sexual abuse.

REVIEW OF LITERTURE

David Finkelhor (2010) has done descriptive study on child maltreatment in united states department of health and human services found that 1 out of 5 girls is a victim of sexual abuse. Study shows that 20% adult female recall sexual abuse incident. 28% had been sexually abused over the course of their lifetime ages between 14 to 17. International Journal of Nursing Education and Research 5(1): January – March 2017 38 Girls are more vulnerable between the ages of 7 and 13. During a one year period in U.S 16% of youth ages 14 to 17 had been sexually victimized.^[6] R. Shashikumar, R C Das (2012) conducted a cross sectional study on factors associated with adolescent sexuality. Study conducted in two co-educational schools of Goa. Total study sample was 642. It comprised

357 (61.93%) girls and 229 (39.07%) boys. 30.08% girls had reported having sexual experience. Average age of first sexual contact for girl was 14.09 years. 41.09% girls and 53.04% boys have the knowledge regarding sex education.^[7]

David J. Miller (2009) did study to assess the awareness of previous campaign in both rural and urban Kenya. A total number of 1195 respondents were interviewed; previous study was conducted in 1999. The findings show levels of awareness and knowledge about sexual abuse increased in adults. Thus, 96% of adults and 80% of children interviewed had heard about child abuse and neglect. A large number of the respondents were able to identify' forms of child abuse without any guidance as it was in the previous study i.e. reading a list of pre coded concepts. The respondents were also able to mention other forms of child' abuse such as verbal abuse, early marriage, and female circumcision, and abortion and sex discrimination. These were some of the concepts used in the campaign. This is a clear demonstration that the campaign had yielded some results.^[8]

METHODS

RESEARCH APPROACH- In this study quantitative research approach was used to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding awareness about Sexual abuse among adolescent girls.

RESEARCH DESIGN- Research design selected for the present study was Pre Experimental Research Design (One-Group Pretest- Post test Design)] **Exp.** Group

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE

In this study the demographic variables taken in to consideration are age, standard, education of father, education of mother, type of family, income, sources of Information and mode of transportation.

RESEARCH SETTING

The present study was be conducted at **Pioneer Montessori High School Barabanki**

POPULATION

Target population- The target population of the study are Adolescent girls studying in school.

Accessible population- The accessible population of the study is High School girls who come under the age of 13-19 years.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLE SIZE

Sample- Sample in the study refers to the Adolescent girls who come under the age of 13-19 years.

Sample Size-Sample size is 30 control group and 30 experimaental group calculate by the(Paired “t” test method).

SAMPLE TECHNIQUE

Random sampling technique was used to select the samples for this study.

DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOL AND SCORING PROCEDURE

The tool consist of two sections:

Section-I: Demographic data

- Age

- Standard
- Education of father
- Education of mother
- Type of family
- Income
- Sources of Information
- Transportation

Section-II Self- Structured Knowledge Questionnaire regarding Sexual Abuse

- 4 Question based on Introduction
- 7 Question based on Causes
- 10 Question based on symptom
- 6 Question based on treatment
- 3 Question based on helpline.

EVALUATION CRITERIA

S.NO.	SCORE	LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE
1.	0-10	Poor knowledge
2.	11-20	Average knowledge
3.	21-30	Good knowledge

RESULTS

There was significant association found between standard of studying ($\chi^2=8.92>P=5.99$) and source of information ($\chi^2=18.94>P=12.48$) at 0.05 level of significance.

Hence hypothesis H_1 is accepted with regards to standard of studying and source of information.

While no association found between age ($\chi^2=8.86<P=12.48$), father educational status ($\chi^2=3.32<P=12.48$), mother educational status ($\chi^2=3.32<P=12.48$), type of family ($\chi^2=0.49<P=5.99$), monthly family income in rs. ($\chi^2=4.11<P=5.99$) and mode of transportation for school ($\chi^2=10.38<P=12.48$) at 0.05 level of significance.

Hence hypothesis H_2 is rejected with regards to age, father educational status mother educational status, type of family, monthly family income in rs., and mode of transportation for school at 0.05 level of significance.

ORGANIZATION OF THE DATA

SECTION I

FREQUENCY AND PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF THE SUBJECT ACCORDING TO SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

N=60

S.No.	Socio Demographic Variables	N	(%)
1	AGE IN YEAR		
a)	13-15 year	32	53.33%
b)	15-17 year	25	41.67%
c)	17-19 year	03	5%
2	STANDARD OF STUDYING		
a)	9 TH	27	45%

b)	10 TH	33	55%
3	FATHER EDUCATIONAL STATUS		
a)	Illiterate	0	0%
b)	Secondary	15	25%
c)	Graduate	35	58.33%
e)	Post graduation	10	16.67%
4.	MOTHER EDUCATIONAL STATUS		
a)	Illiterate	0	0%
b)	Secondary	25	41.67%
c)	Graduate	23	38.33%
d)	Post graduation	12	20%
5.	TYPE OF FAMILY		
a)	Nuclear	40	66.67%
b)	Joint	20	33.33%
c)	Other	0	0%
6.	MONTHLY FAMILY INCOME IN RS		
a)	Less Than 10,000	0	0%
b)	10,001-15,000	32	53.33%
c)	Above 15,001	28	46.67%
7.	MODE OF TRANSPORTATION FOR SCHOOL		
a)	School Bus	18	30%
b)	Personal Convey	32	53.33%
c)	Public Transport	10	16.67%
d)	Others	0	0%
8.	SOURCE OF INFORMATION		
a)	Mass Media	31	51.67%
b)	Health Personals	15	25%
c)	Family & Friends	14	23.33%
d)	Others	0	0%

SECTION –II

OBJECTIVE 1:- TO ASSESS THE PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE REGARDING SEXUAL ABUSE AMONG ADOLESCENT GIRLS

Overall analysis to assess the pre-test and post test level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls using mean score and standard deviation.

N=60

Level of Knowledge	PRE TEST				POST TEST			
	(n)	(%)	Mean	SD	(n)	(%)	Mean	SD
Poor (0-10)	12	20%	13.88	4.85	2	3.33%	20.13	3.66
Average (11-20)	39	65%			31	51.67%		
Good (21-30)	9	15%			27	45%		

SECTION III

OBJECTIVE 2- TO EVALUATE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF STRUCTURED TEACHING PROGRAMME ON KNOWLEDGE REGARDING SEXUAL ABUSE AMONG ADOLESCENT GIRLS

Paired “t” test analysis to evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls

N=60

Knowledge score	Mean	SD	“t” Value	Mean difference	D F	Table value	Significance
Pre test	13.88	4.85	7.82	6.25	59	1.67	P< 0.05 Significance
Post test	20.13	3.66					

SECTION-IV

OBJECTIVE 3- TO FIND OUT THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN PRE-TEST LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE REGARDING SEXUAL ABUSE AMONG ADOLESCENT GIRLS WITH THEIR SELECTED SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES.

Chi-square analysis to find out association between pre test level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls with their selected socio demographic variables.

N=60

S. N.	Demographic variables	LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE			Chi square test	D F	Critical value at P>0.05	Inference
		Poor	Average	Good				
		n 12	n 39	n 9				
1) AGE (IN YEAR)								
A.	13-15	10	17	5	8.86	4	12.48	Not Significant
B.	15-17	1	21	3				
C.	17-19 year	1	1	1				
2) STANDARD OF STUDYING								
A.	9 TH	10	14	3	8.92	2	5.99	Significant
B.	10 TH	2	25	6				
3) FATHER EDUCATIONAL STATUS								
A.	Illiterate	0	0	0	3.32	4	12.48	

B.	Secondary	2	10	3				Not Significant
C.	Graduate	6	24	5				
D.	Post graduation	4	5	1				
4) MOTHER EDUCATIONAL STATUS								
A.	Illiterate	0	0	0	11.78	4	12.48	Not Significant
B.	Secondary	7	15	3				
C.	Graduate	1	20	2				
D.	Post graduation	4	4	4				
5) TYPE OF FAMILY								
A.	Nuclear	9	25	6	0.49	2	5.99	Not Significant
B.	Joint	3	14	3				
C.	Other	0	0	0				
MONTHLY FAMILY INCOME IN RS.								
A.	Less Than 10,000	0	0	0	4.11	2	5.99	Not Significant
B.	10,001-15,000	7	23	2				
C.	Above 15,001	5	16	7				
7) MODE OF TRANSPORTATION FOR SCHOOL								
A.	School Bus	1	11	6	10.38	4	12.48	Not Significant
B.	Personal Convey	7	23	2				
C.	Public Transport	4	5	1				
D.	Others	0	0	0				
8) SOURCE OF INFORMATION								
A.	Mass Media	2	28	1	18.94	4	12.48	Significant
B.	Health Personals	5	5	5				
C.	Family & Friends	5	6	3				
D.	Others	0	0	0				

DISCUSSION

Objective-1

To assess the pre-test and post-test level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls

zenodo

www.scientificjournal.in

YEAR: 2026

VOLUME: 4

ISSUE: 1

ISSN: 3107-4162

Depicts that in pre test among 6 participants majority 39 (65%) had average knowledge regarding sexual abuse, 12(20%) had good knowledge regarding sexual abuse and only 9 (15%) had poor knowledge regarding sexual abuse. However in post- test knowledge regarding sexual abuse was increase, majority 31(51.67%) participant had average knowledge regarding sexual abuse, 27(45%) had good knowledge regarding sexual abuse and only 2(33.33%) had poor knowledge regarding sexual abuse.

The corresponding study is supported by study done by Kaverin Nair (2024) to assess the knowledge regarding level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls selected school of Bhopal. After obtaining permission from the principal, the investigator selected 60 samples by using Random sampling technique. Self structured Questionnaire was used to collect the demographic variables of adolescent students. The result of the study shows majority 48 (80%) students had poor knowledge, 12(20%) students had average knowledge and none of the students had good knowledge regarding prevention of sexual abuse. However in post- test knowledge score regarding sexual abuse was increase, majority 54(90%) students had average knowledge and only 6(10%) students had good knowledge regarding sexual abuse. Hence hypothesis H1 is accepted.

Objective-2

To evaluate the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls

Depicts the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse. In which pre test mean is 13.88 and in post test mean is 20.13. The standard deviation of Pre-test is 4.85 and post test is 3.66. This means that there is a significant improvement in the knowledge of the subjects after the administration of structured teaching programme.

A corresponding study supported above finding done by Neelima Mehta (2023) to assess effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent students at Govt. higher secondary school of Rishikesh. A quantitative research approach and pre experimental one group pre test post test research design was adopted to conduct study. Structured knowledge questionnaire was used to collect the data. Pre test was taken on first day followed by structured teaching programme to group and then post test was taken after seven days. In pre test majority students (65%) had average level of knowledge but in post test majority (55%) had good level of knowledge. There was significant difference between the mean pre test and post test knowledge score ($t = 9.590$, $p = 0.0001$) at $p < 0.05$. Structured teaching program was highly effective in enhancing the knowledge of adolescent students regarding sexual abuse.

Objective-3

To find out the association between pre-test level of knowledge regarding sexual abuse among adolescent girls with their selected socio-demographic variables.

Reveals that there was significant association found between standard of studying ($\chi^2=8.92 > P=5.99$) and source of information ($\chi^2=18.94 > P=12.48$) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence hypothesis H1 is accepted with regards to standard of studying and source of information.

While no association found between age ($\chi^2=8.86 < P=12.48$), father educational status ($\chi^2=3.32 < P=12.48$), mother educational status ($\chi^2=3.32 < P=12.48$), type of family ($\chi^2=0.49 < P=5.99$), monthly family income in rs. ($\chi^2=4.11 < P=5.99$) and mode of transportation for school ($\chi^2=10.38 < P=12.48$) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence hypothesis H2 is rejected with regards to age, father educational status mother educational status, type of family, monthly family income in rs., and mode of transportation for school at 0.05 level of significance.

REFERENCES

1. Berk, Laura E. Infants, children and adolescents. 3rd edition: Bacon; 2005. Adolescent Health and Development (AHD) [Serial online] May 2008, www.whoindia.org/en/Section6/Section425.htm
2. Robert GE, Studies in Adolescence, New York, 1963. McGraw-Hill Book Company; Volume: [p.235].
3. Kaitre Loveleen dr. women and child development of India. Study on child abuse 20007:5-7.
4. Global Prevalence of Child Sexual Abuse 2009, www.journalistsresource.org/studies/com reviewed on 15/11/2011.
5. Conte, J. (2009). Prevalence of sexual abuse. Journal of clinical psychology, Oct 2009;2(6):21-31
6. Davis Finkelhor. Study on child maltreatment in unites states. journal of nursing. Reviewed on 14/9/2010 (5):263.
7. R. Shashikumar, R.C. Das study on factors associated with adolescent sexuality. Goa. Journal of school of nursing. 2012 (5); 21-22.
8. David J. Miller. study to assess the awareness of previous campaign in both rural and urban Kenya. February 2009:35